

RESIDUAL STRESSES IN THERMOPLASTIC BONDING TO METALS: EXPERIMENTS AND MODELING

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SUMMARY: The ability to create strong joints between thermoplastics and metals offers many advantages. Differential properties between the polymer and metal generate residual stresses during cooling. In our study, both amorphous thermoplastic thin films and semi-crystalline thermoplastic thin films are joined to metal strips and the curvature is measured during controlled cooling. A series of five designed experiments uses a fast cooling (~ 30 °C/second) and slow cooling ($\sim 4.5 - 10$ °C/minute) to create different residual stresses. Experimental evidence shows that the residual stresses begin to develop at ~ 190 °C for amorphous *Poly Ether Imide* (PEI, $T_g = 210$ °C), but at ~ 255 °C for semi-crystalline *Poly Ether Ether Ketone* (PEEK, $T_g = 143$ °C). A mechanics based curvature model, combined with the elasticity and viscoelasticity of thermoplastics, successfully predicts the residual stress development. An elastic behavior is exhibited during the fast cooling (~ 30 °C/second), whereas a viscoelastic behavior occurs during slow cooling (~ 4.5 °C/minute).

KEYWORDS: residual stress; thermoplastic adhesive bonding; elastic/viscoelastic

INTRODUCTION

Hot-melt thermoplastic adhesives are finding more applications in bonding various materials. One of the most important applications is to create structural joints between thermoplastics and metals. Thermoplastic joining to metals can also be extended to create joints in-situ in manufacture of a thermoplastic part such as during injection molding. In addition, the potential for fast joining together with significantly better durability than thermoset based joints makes the thermoplastic bonding approach an attractive option for future manufacturing [1]. In our earlier studies, a thin-film thermoplastic-metal joining process was investigated extensively [1-4]. The surface preparation, contact pressure during consolidation, heating and cooling rates, hold times at melt and recrystallization temperature, effect of bond line thickness and uniformity, and anodization to increase durability were included in the process development. This study is intended to investigate the residual stress development associated with thin-film thermoplastic-metal bonding.

Residual stresses generated at the polymer-metal interface during bonding can influence joint strength and durability significantly. The presence of high internal stresses at the interface can cause loss of adhesion and/or cracking. For thermoplastic adhesive bonding to metals, differential properties between polymer and metal generate residual stresses during the cooling process. A sound experimental and theoretical understanding of the relationship

between residual stress development and the bonding process will contribute to reducing the processing time, improving the processing and resulting joint performance.

The role of residual stresses in polymers has been recognized as an important issue in several related areas, such as coatings, adhesive bonding, and polymeric composites. Moran *et al.* [5] investigated the residual stress in thermoplastic coating films. Chapman *et al.* [6] developed a model to predict residual stresses in thermoplastic composites. However, no model has been developed to describe the residual stress development in thermoplastic polymer-metal bonding during processing. This study develops and experimentally validates a model for predicting the residual stress evolution during processing.

EXPERIMENTAL

Design of Experiment

In this study, a beam curvature method was employed to investigate the residual stress development at the polymer-metal interface. A thermoplastic thin-film was heated to melt and bonded to a metal strip. During the subsequent cooling process, a curvature developed because of the differential properties of the polymer and metal.

The polymers used in this study are semi-crystalline *Poly Ether Ether Ketone* (Westlake Plastic company, PEEK 450G, 0.127 mm thick) and amorphous *Poly Ether Imide* (PEI, GE, Ultem 1000, 0.127 mm thick). Both of them exhibit excellent physical properties compared to most other engineering polymers, such as higher strength and rigidity at room and elevated temperature. The superior properties make them ideal polymers for use in various applications, including adhesive bonding.

In this study, a thin steel strip (Precision Brand, 0.102 mm thick) is used as the substrate for bonding the polymers.

The experiments were performed in a computer controlled press. The polymer-metal beam sample (50 x 5mm) was placed in between the two relatively large hot platens (228 x 228mm) of the press. Figure 1 shows a schematic diagram of the experimental set-up. The two hot platens were brought very close to each other (~12mm) to provide a uniform temperature field. Two thermocouples located at different positions gave very close temperature measurements (Figure 2). The temperature difference between the two thermocouples was ~10 °C above 240 °C and ~20 °C below 240 °C. The curvature was monitored along with the temperature using a high resolution camera and data acquisition system during the cooling process.

Based on the bonding processes developed in our laboratory, three typical process cycles of PEEK/steel bonding and two typical process cycles of PEI/steel bonding were investigated, and were identified as cycle #1 through #5. Table 1 shows the basic processing parameters. For PEEK, its crystallinity and the process cooling rate were considered as important factors in designing the process cycles. The purpose of the process cycle #1 was to investigate a fast cooling process which resulted in very low crystallinity. The process cycle #3 was to simulate the residual stress effects of a slow cooling process which produced ~35% crystallinity by weight determined using differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) [2]. The process cycle #2 would produce approximately the same crystallinity as the cycle #3 but included a fast

cooling process from 210 °C to room temperature. The process cycles #4 and #5 are for amorphous PEI.

Using the experimental setup (Figure 1) and process cycles #1 through #5, the evolution of curvature with temperature produced in the steel substrate was measured. The curvatures with the elastic properties of the steel are used to calculate the residual stress in the film using [7]

Figure 1 Experimental setup

Figure 2 Temperature profile during cooling

Table 1 Polymer film-steel strip bonding process

Process cycle	Polymer	Bonding Processing parameters
#1	PEEK	heat to 370 °C, hold for 20 minutes, fast cooling (~30 °C/second) to room temperature
#2	PEEK	heat to 370 °C, hold for 20 minutes, slow cooling (~4.5 °C/minute) to 210 °C, fast cooling (~30 °C/second) to room temperature
#3	PEEK	heat to 370 °C, hold for 20 minutes, slow cooling (~4.5 - 10 °C/minute) to room temperature
#4	PEI	heat to 370 °C, hold for 15 minutes, fast cooling (~30 °C/second) to room temperature
#5	PEI	heat to 370 °C, hold for 15 minutes, slow cooling (~4.5-10 °C/minute) to room temperature

$$\sigma_i = \frac{E_m h^3}{6c(h+c)(1-\gamma_m)} \frac{1}{r(T_i)} \quad (1)$$

where σ_i : residual stress

T_i : temperature

E_m : elastic modulus of the steel strip

h : the thickness of the steel strip

c : the thickness of the polymer

$r(T_i)$: radius of the curvature

γ_m : Poisson's ratio of the steel strip

Obviously the curvature and residual stress will change during the cooling process. It will be shown in the modeling section that the curvature and residual stress development is not completely described by equation (1) alone.

Experimental Results

The residual stresses in the film calculated using equation (1) with measured curvatures are presented in Figure 3 for experimental process cycles #1 through #5 for PEEK and PEI. In Figure 3, the small standard deviations of the average residual stress results demonstrate the repeatability of the experiments. Errors in the experiments introduced by the measurements of temperature and curvatures were estimated below 15 percent. Comparing the experimental results of process cycle #1, #2 and #3 for PEEK, we can conclude that high crystallinity (corresponding to high elastic modulus) resulting from the initial slow cooling to 210 °C results in high residual stresses. Process cycle #2 produce higher residual stress than process cycle #3. For PEI, the residual stress difference between slow cooling and fast cooling is smaller compared to the corresponding difference in residual stresses for PEEK.

Figure 3 Residual stress comparison of experiments with model

The curvature change with temperature is shown in Figure 4 for PEI film-steel strip bonding and in Figure 5 for PEEK film-steel strip bonding. Both of them are obtained from slow cooling experiments (process cycle #3 and #5). The curvature as a result of residual stresses begins to develop at $\sim 190^\circ\text{C}$ for amorphous PEI ($T_g = 210^\circ\text{C}$), but at $\sim 255^\circ\text{C}$ for semi-crystalline PEEK ($T_g = 143^\circ\text{C}$).

Figure 4 Curvature development of PEI film-steel strip bonding during slow cooling (process cycle #5)

Figure 5 Curvature development of PEEK film-steel strip bonding during slow cooling (process cycle #3)

MODELING AND ANALYSIS

The residual stress is initiated by the differential thermal shrinkage between the polymer and metal. In the melt region, the polymer behaves as a viscous liquid and is considered to be in a stress-free state. As it is cooled down to its rubbery region, a curvature begins to develop. The development of the residual stresses during cooling is closely related to the elastic and viscoelastic properties of the polymer and the cooling rate. In this section, an elastic model is developed with potential applicability for a fast cooling process that allows little stress relaxation. For the slow cooling process, a Maxwell stress relaxation model was used to explain the residual stress development in the glass transition region. In addition, the shrinkage due to crystallization of PEEK was relatively small and neglected. The residual stress is assumed to be uniform along the whole length of the sample.

Elastic Model

An incremental elastic model is described below. At a temperature step T_i , the incremental stress $\Delta\sigma_i$ is generated by the incremental thermal strain $\Delta\varepsilon_i$

$$\Delta\varepsilon_i = (\alpha_p - \alpha_m)\Delta T_i \quad (2)$$

$$\Delta\sigma_i = -\frac{E_p(T_i)\Delta\varepsilon_i}{(1 - \gamma_p)} \quad (3)$$

where α_p : thermal expansion coefficient of the polymer

α_m : thermal expansion coefficient of the metal

$E_p(T_i)$: elastic modulus of the polymer at temperature T_i

γ_p : Poisson's ratio of the polymer

Adding this incremental stress to the previous stress σ_{i-1} , the present stress σ_i will be

$$\sigma_i = \sigma_{i-1} + \Delta\sigma_i \quad (4)$$

Considering the curvature-introduced contraction in the polymer [7], the present curvature will be

$$\frac{1}{r(T_i)} = \frac{\sigma_i}{\frac{E_m h^3}{6c(h+c)(1-\gamma_m)} + \frac{(h+c)E_p(T_i)}{2(1-\gamma_p)}} \quad (5)$$

The residual stress and curvature at each temperature step are calculated using equation (4) and (5). The actual residual stress at a temperature step is a little lower than the above calculated stress because of the curvature-introduced contraction in the polymer. The residual stresses are recalculated using equation (1) with the calculated curvatures from equation (5).

This elastic model is employed to calculate the curvature and residual stresses for all of our five process cycles. In Figure 3, it is shown that the elastic model matches the experimental results for process cycle #1, #2 and #4. However, the elastic model predicts higher residual stresses for process cycle #3 and #5 than the experiments. It is also noticed in Figure 4 and 5 that the calculated curvature using this elastic model begins to be higher than the experimental results in the glass transition region of the slow cooling process cycle #3 and #5.

Viscoelastic Model and Analysis

During a slow cooling process, three temperature regions are analyzed. *Region I* is above glass transition temperature of the polymer. The residual stress level is relatively low in region I because the thermal shrinkage results in a small strain and the elastic modulus of the polymer is also very low. Therefore, an elastic model successfully explains the curvature development in this range (see region I of Figure 5). However, in *region II*, the glass transition region, a rapid increase of the elastic modulus of the polymer can cause a large increase of the residual stress level. The residual stress level is close to the yield strength of the polymer in this region. A stress relaxation can be noticed in region II of Figure 4 and 5. In *region III*, below glass transition temperature, the elastic modulus of the polymer will not change significantly with temperature, but its yield strength will increase rapidly with temperature. The elastic model is satisfactory in region III. Figure 6 shows the comparison of the calculated elastic residual stress and the yield strength of the polymer during cooling.

The stress relaxation in *region II* depends upon the cooling rate. That is why a fast cooling in this region allows very little relaxation and the elastic model successfully predicts the corresponding residual stresses. Process cycle #2 of Figure 3 shows a comparison of the elastic model and experiments.

Figure 6 Comparison of calculated elastic residual stress with the yield strength of PEEK

The Maxwell model is combined with the Boltzmann superposition principle to analyze the stress relaxation in the glass transition region (*region II*). The stress relaxation begins at temperature T_b and ends at temperature T_e . For PEEK, $T_b = 210$ °C and $T_e = 140$ °C were determined through comparing the experimental curvature results with the calculated results using the elastic model. The residual stress σ_i at temperature T_i is

$$\sigma_i = \sigma_e + \Delta\sigma_I e^{-t_i/\tau_i} \quad (6)$$

$$\Delta\sigma_I = \Delta\sigma_i + \Delta\sigma_{I-1} e^{-t_{i-1}/\tau_{i-1}} \quad (7)$$

The σ_e is the residual stress at T_b and will not undergo relaxation. $\Delta\sigma_i$ is the residual stress increase from the previous temperature T_{i-1} to the present temperature T_i . The total stress $\Delta\sigma_I$ without σ_e will relax. t_i is the elapsed time at the present temperature step. τ_i is the relaxation time associated to the present temperature, which can be determined using the dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA) experiments.

$$\tan \delta_i = \frac{E''(T_i)}{E'(T_i)} = \frac{1}{\tau_i \omega} \quad (8)$$

where E'' : loss modulus

E' : storage modulus

$\tan \delta_i$: tangent of the phase angle

ω : measurement frequency

Biddlestone *et al.* [8] investigated the dynamic mechanical property of PEI. The dynamic mechanical properties of PEEK were obtained from Krishnaswamy *et al.* [9]. The parameters

for our models listed in Table 2 were obtained using ASTM standards by the polymer manufacturers.

Table 2 Materials' data

material	elastic modulus (GPa)	Poisson's ratio	thermal expansion coefficient ($10^{-5} / ^\circ \text{C}$)
PEEK (450G)	4.05 (~35 %) 2.70 (~0 %)	0.4	4.68 ($T < T_g$) 10.8 ($T > T_g$)
PEI (Ultem 1000)	3.30	0.36	5.58 ($T < T_g$) ~10. ($T > T_g$)
Steel	190	0.30	1.5

The elastic modulus of polymer is measured at room temperature.

(%) = crystallinity

Figures 4 and 5 compare the viscoelastic+elastic model, the elastic model and the experimental curvatures for PEI and PEEK in a slow cooling process. The viscoelastic+elastic model correctly explains the curvature development during the slow cooling process.

CONCLUSIONS

Based on development of beam curvature during cooling for an amorphous thermoplastic (PEI) and a semi-crystalline thermoplastic (PEEK), the experimental study combined with the model and analysis has resulted in the following key conclusions. First, the curvature experiments successfully reveal the residual stress development during thermoplastic bonding to metals. Second, the elastic model can be used to correctly predict the residual stresses for fast cooling processes (~30 °C/second). Finally, the viscoelastic+elastic model correctly predicts the curvature change and the residual stress development with temperature for slow cooling process (~4.5 - 10 °C /minute). The model developed and the results can be used in residual stress analysis and optimization of thermoplastic-metal bonding.

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